

Studying the quality of organizational entrepreneurship University International of Chabahar

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Abstract

Today, the entrepreneurial university, as the third generation of universities, is entrusted with the mission of promoting economic and social development. Therefore, understanding this mission and how to realize it within traditional universities is of particular importance. According to the theoretical framework, an entrepreneurial university has an independent identity and distinct characteristics. As an organization, it also possesses organizational traits; thus, transforming the traditional organizational features of universities toward corporate entrepreneurship can convert a traditional university into an entrepreneurial one. This study aimed to examine the quality of corporate entrepreneurship at Chabahar International University. In terms of purpose, the research is applied; in terms of control over variables, it is non-experimental; and it falls under the category of descriptive-correlational studies. The data are quantitative and were collected through a survey conducted among the employees of Chabahar International University. The statistical population includes all 54 employees of the university. Due to the limited population size, a census sampling method was used, and the sample size equaled the population size (54 individuals). A total of 54 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 39 were returned and deemed usable, while 15 were either not returned or unusable.

For data analysis, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and one-sample t-test were used. The findings indicate that, in terms of corporate entrepreneurship quality at the university, variables such as individual attitude, entrepreneurial culture, flexibility, reward system, entrepreneurial leadership, and organizational practices are in favorable condition.

Keywords: Corporate Entrepreneurship, International University, Quality of Entrepreneurship, Chabahar City.

Introduction

One of the defining features of today's economy is its rapid pace of change, and only countries with innovative and risk-taking organizational entrepreneurs can become economically strong and successful (Ahmadpour Daryani & Moghimi, 2010). In fact, entrepreneurship is considered a symbol of innovation and success in commercial affairs, and entrepreneurs are pioneers who, through their novel ideas, bring about fundamental transformations in administrative systems and improve their efficiency and effectiveness (Abtin, 2011; Ahmadpour Daryani, 2004). This indicates that the economy is influenced by entrepreneurship, and if organizations fail to keep up with fast-paced global changes, they will stagnate and inevitably lose their relevance and dissolve over time (Partonia, 2013; Yazdi Moghaddam, 2013).

Therefore, organizations need to replace traditional production methods with innovative approaches in order to meet the endless demands of customers, protect their competitive advantage, and remain in the competitive arena (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2008). On the other hand, the presence of entrepreneurial and development-oriented managers fosters a spirit of entrepreneurship and creates an entrepreneurial environment within organizations. Such leaders can face organizational challenges with foresight and lead the country toward sustainability and stability by securing significant shares in global markets (Asadzadeh et al., 2018).

For this reason, many management experts and theorists began to explain organizational entrepreneurship in the early 1970s. However, it wasn't until the early 1980s that it gained serious recognition among researchers (Nahid, 2009). Management thinkers have since adopted a process-oriented approach to entrepreneurial management and the entrepreneurial environment within existing organizations (Fakhari et al., 2021). In order to survive, create value, perform better, and achieve goals, organizations need innovation, proactivity, risk-taking, and overall entrepreneurship (Bagheri Majd et al., 2018).

One of the key strategies for organizations to enhance their performance is institutional entrepreneurship and the presence of entrepreneurial individuals, as organizational entrepreneurship can positively impact performance (Kiakajouri & Fazeli Veysari, 2010). Bureaucratic and conservative management, common in public sector organizations, stemming from structural constraints, dominant organizational culture, and traditional practices, has become a barrier to organizational entrepreneurship (Ahmadpour Daryani, 2008; Kardanayij et al., 2012). This has resulted in the lack of entrepreneurship in the public sector and weakened its performance (Yazdi Moghaddam, 2013).

Today, entrepreneurial universities pursue two main goals: first, training future entrepreneurs and individuals who will launch businesses, and second, promoting an entrepreneurial spirit among students across all disciplines (Arasti et al., 2015). They also engage in entrepreneurial activities such as establishing business incubators, creating technology parks, and involving students in these institutions (Jame Asl et al., 2016). An entrepreneurial university is an institution that fosters the creation of new businesses by supporting entrepreneurial individuals (Behzadi et al., 2014).

These universities provide an ecosystem where investors can capitalize on opportunities, and students are expected to simultaneously acquire knowledge, knowledge management skills, and entrepreneurial management in order to actively engage in industry (Abesi et al., 2016). The emergence of entrepreneurial universities has transformed previously disconnected institutions into ones closely linked with industry and society (Hassan et al., 2021). Entrepreneurial universities inject the knowledge they produce into the economic and industrial sectors of society (Lu et al., 2021).

By 2014, MIT alumni had founded more than 30,000 active companies, created 4.6 million jobs, and generated approximately \$1.9 trillion in annual revenue (Chaudhuri et al., 2024). MIT continues to monitor the status of its alumni and maintains precise data on the companies they establish, their level of entrepreneurship, and revenue distribution by industry type (Ketikidis et al., 2012). In contrast, most universities in Iran are not even aware of the employment status of their recent graduates (Marzban et al., 2013). The latest global university systems focus on third-generation entrepreneurial universities (Seyfried et al., 2019). Many top global universities earn significant revenue from licensing their intellectual property. For example, in 2012, Northwestern University earned \$161 million, Columbia University \$154 million, and New York University \$113 million from such sources (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2001).

In Iran, most universities still operate as second-generation research-oriented institutions and do little in terms of commercializing research, training entrepreneurs, or evolving into third-generation entrepreneurial universities (Akbari Dehghan et al., 2021). The commercialization activities of domestic universities are often limited to establishing science and technology parks, which contribute minimally to the business market (Mazdeh et al., 2013). Therefore, creating innovative activities through the establishment of entrepreneurial universities is essential. Without such institutions, the results of scientific research will merely be archived in libraries and rarely transformed into innovative products or services (Sarabi et al., 2012).

The Chabahar International University was established in 2002 with the mission of preparing and educating responsible, creative, and skilled students aligned with Islamic values and human ideals. It has designed academic programs to meet the demands of today's real world while upholding the highest academic standards. The university is built on values and objectives such as belief in a knowledge-based, research-oriented institution; providing a suitable and appealing environment to discourage students from seeking education abroad; training specialized professionals for the country, especially in free trade zones; promoting national culture alongside knowledge and individual skill development; supporting students' success through planning and services; and strengthening academic and research links with reputable national and international institutions.

The current study is significant for the following reasons:

Understanding the positive or negative educational outcomes of Chabahar International University and the impact of entrepreneurship in its educational programs is essential. If weaknesses exist, modifying entrepreneurship education can improve outcomes and contribute to organizational entrepreneurship development in the region. Since all companies and organizations in the study area are in some way connected to the Chabahar Free Trade-Industrial Zone, and the university is the only educational institution in the area, the findings of this research can significantly impact the community.

The university's overarching policy emphasizes becoming an entrepreneurial university. However, to achieve this goal, all contributing factors must be regularly assessed to facilitate progress. Therefore, the main objective of this research is to evaluate the quality of various indicators related to transforming Chabahar International University into an

entrepreneurial institution. Assessing the quality of organizational entrepreneurship at this university is vital, as it directly affects students' academic experiences, the university's reputation, and its scientific and research rankings.

Universities play a central role in the global competition in higher education. Improving the quality of organizational entrepreneurship at Chabahr University can enhance its global appeal and attract international students and researchers. Research in this field can also promote an entrepreneurial culture at the university. An entrepreneurial organizational culture fosters innovation, flexibility, and the empowerment of staff and students, driving the university toward transformation. The research objectives are outlined as follows:

Main Objective:

To study the quality of organizational entrepreneurship at Chabahr International University.

Sub-Objectives:

1. To study the quality of the **organizational behavior** variable at Chabahr International University.
2. To study the quality of the **individual attitude** variable at Chabahr International University.
3. To study the quality of the **flexibility** variable at Chabahr International University.
4. To study the quality of the **reward system** variable at Chabahr International University.
5. To study the quality of the **entrepreneurial leadership** variable at Chabahr International University.
6. To study the quality of the **entrepreneurial culture** variable at Chabahr International University.

Theoretical Framework

The term *entrepreneurship* originates from the French word “*entreprendre*”, meaning *to undertake*. According to Webster's Collegiate Dictionary, an entrepreneur is someone who undertakes the organization, administration, and risk of a business activity. Entrepreneurship is a process that leads to the creation of satisfaction or new demand. It refers to the process of creating value through the formation of a unique set of resources to take advantage of opportunities.

An *independent entrepreneur* is an individual who takes primary responsibility for mobilizing the necessary resources to launch or grow a business, focusing on innovation and developing new products or services. In other words, an entrepreneur is a person who establishes and manages a business, with the primary goal of profit and growth. The core characteristic of an entrepreneur is innovation (Sayad Bidehendi, 2012).

Numerous scholars have defined entrepreneurship in various ways, tailoring their definitions to fit the context of their research. Entrepreneurship has both social and economic dimensions. Today, it is considered not only a vital factor in economic development but also a driver of investment spirit and labor productivity. Therefore, promoting entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial culture is seen as an economic, social, and political necessity (Zarei Pahneh Kalayee, Ahmadpour, & Charmian Langroudi, 2013).

Abtin (2011), quoting Moghimi (2004), believes that entrepreneurship is a concept as old as human creation itself. A review of entrepreneurship literature shows that economists were the first to address the concept in their theories. Over time, scholars from psychology, management, sociology, and anthropology also began to explore its various aspects.

Economists regard entrepreneurship as the engine of economic development. Psychological studies focus on how individual traits relate to motivation and entrepreneurial performance. Sociologists examine the influence of religion, ethnicity, and social groupings on entrepreneurial activity, while anthropologists emphasize the roles of culture and social relationships. Management scholars have explored entrepreneurial management and the creation of entrepreneurial environments within organizations (Abtin, 2011).

Wolf (1995) stated that both personal and organizational variables — such as technology, structure, strategy, and culture — along with environmental variables, influence innovation, creativity, and entrepreneurship within organizations. Entrepreneurship is a process in which creativity and innovation are central components.

Ahmadpour and Moghimi (2009) referenced various definitions in their book. For instance, Peter Drucker (1985) defined entrepreneurship as an innovative act that utilizes existing resources to create new capacity for wealth generation. Similarly, Schumpeter viewed entrepreneurship as introducing new products, production methods, markets, resources, or organizational structures (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2001).

Robert Ronstadt (1984) defined entrepreneurship as a dynamic process aimed at capital formation, driven by someone willing to risk time or job opportunities in pursuit of value through a product or service (Shah Hosseini, 2007). Thompson (2000) viewed entrepreneurship as a process that creates a new member and new value using creativity, time, resources, risk, and other factors.

In summary, based on the presented definitions, it can be claimed that without entrepreneurship, human societies would have an incomplete understanding of organizations, markets, and business transactions — since entrepreneurs are the producers of ideas (Nahid, 2009).

Among the various categorizations of entrepreneurship, the classification by *Cornwall and Perlman* is more commonly applied in the field of management.

1. Individual Entrepreneurship

Identifying who entrepreneurs are and what they must do to be considered as such has long been the focal point of many discussions. In fact, most people labeled as entrepreneurs consider themselves worthy of the title. One entrepreneur from the Midwestern United States, while addressing a group of future entrepreneurs, went so far as to claim that "there is no such thing as an entrepreneur." This assertion stems from the idea that entrepreneurship is not a simple concept. It is multifaceted, and defining exactly what an entrepreneur does is indeed complex. Inventors, lawyers, businesspeople, educators, and doctors can all be entrepreneurs.

If we shift our focus from *who* the entrepreneur is to *what* the entrepreneur does, the definition becomes clearer. According to Ronstadt, the entrepreneurial process is about creating wealth. With this perspective, identifying an entrepreneur becomes significantly easier: an entrepreneur is someone who establishes, acquires, or gains representation of an independent organization.

In essence, individual entrepreneurship refers to a situation in which a person creates an independent business or obtains a franchise by identifying opportunities and mobilizing the necessary resources. Their focus is on innovation, process development, and the creation of new products or services (Ahmadpour Daryani, 2008).

2. Intrapreneurship (Corporate Entrepreneurship)

Intrapreneurship is the responsibility of realizing innovative initiatives *within* an existing organization. In other words, intrapreneurship is the process by which innovative products or processes emerge through the cultivation and maintenance of an entrepreneurial culture within an already established organization (Karbasiyan, Sharafat, Valadkhani, Azimzadegan, 2002).

This form of entrepreneurship involves fostering entrepreneurial behavior within an existing organization. It is a process through which new products, services, or processes are developed by creating an internal entrepreneurial culture. In intrapreneurship, a company or organization provides an environment where members are encouraged to participate in entrepreneurial activities, ultimately leading to the emergence of innovative products, services, or processes (Moghimi, 2008).

3. Corporate Entrepreneurship (Organizational Entrepreneurship)

The term Corporate Entrepreneurship was first coined by Pinckett (1978), referring to entrepreneurs within large organizations. However, as entrepreneurship expanded within organizations and as significant advances were made through the implementation of entrepreneurship, its definitions and concepts evolved. It has since reached a stage of maturity and development. Therefore, corporate entrepreneurship can be defined as a process that drives organizational activities towards creativity, innovation, risk-taking, and leadership (Hadi Zadeh Moghaddam, Rahimi Filabadi, 2005).

Researchers and scholars have provided various definitions of corporate entrepreneurship, some of which are summarized below:

- **Kerr (1996):** A process of creating new businesses within formal organizations to enhance profitability and strengthen competitive position.
- **Koven & Miles (1999):** The presence of innovation, combined with the willingness to revive or purposefully re-identify organizations, markets, or industries to create or maintain a competitive advantage.
- **Von Hippel (1977):** Activities aimed at establishing new business ventures for an organization, which secure the organization by implementing high-risk internal or external ventures.
- **Frey (1993):** Corporate entrepreneurship is a process that fosters innovation in products and processes by introducing an entrepreneurial culture within an organization.
- **Bergman:** Corporate entrepreneurship refers to a process where organizations use their set of opportunities and competencies to diversify products and ultimately foster organizational growth (Kyakjuri, Fadelis Visari, 2009).

Today, **corporate entrepreneurship** is a major concern for many managers in organizations. Utilizing the innovative ideas and thoughts of entrepreneurial employees can lead to significant transformations within organizations and help drive the wheels of economic development. Additionally, a look at successful organizations reveals that, in order to outperform in global competition and gain a major share of the business market, these organizations have extended entrepreneurial behavior and culture across all organizational levels. This involves allocating financial resources, creating motivation, planning, policy-making, supporting managers, and establishing entrepreneurial teams within the

organization. These actions have led to the creation of new business opportunities and greater movement in global markets.

In fact, corporate entrepreneurship can be seen as a key factor that bridges innovation and economic development. Competent and specialized employees are the strong arms of organizational managers, helping them overcome adverse environmental conditions, resolve organizational challenges, and reach innovative solutions, thereby enhancing production quality in global competition (Soheila Partonia, 2012).

Methods for Developing Corporate Entrepreneurship:

1. Developing Vision
2. Encouraging Innovation
3. Creating an Entrepreneurial Atmosphere within the Organization
4. Developing Entrepreneurial Teams
5. Committing the Organization to Entrepreneurship
6. Defining the Type of Entrepreneurship within the Organization
7. Developing an Entrepreneurial Culture
8. Identifying Entrepreneurial Talent
9. Rewarding Corporate Entrepreneurs (Sarabi, Abedui, & Frotan, 2012).

Many believe that entrepreneurship is the driving force behind the economic development of both developed and developing countries. Given the importance of entrepreneurship, wealth generation, technological development, and productive employment, entrepreneurship is seen as a process of innovation, creating new ventures by discovering opportunities and utilizing resources. This process requires planning within educational and training systems, ensuring graduates are capable of leveraging their skills to create value and generate income. The first academic revolution occurred in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, during which research became an official duty of universities, and educational activities previously conducted informally in colleges and scientific communities were incorporated into formal university systems. As a result, modern universities gained a new identity, emphasizing the integration of education and research (Kordnaji, Ahmadi, Ghorbani, & Niakan Lahiji, 2012).

The third academic revolution emerged with new missions for universities, moving beyond the second revolution. It highlighted the economic role of universities in promoting economic growth through collaborations with government and industry. Universities are now expected to foster creativity and critical thinking, swiftly addressing the needs of individuals, solving problems independently or collaboratively, and laying the foundation for sustainable development in the country. In 1984, the term "entrepreneurial university" was introduced by Tekin to describe universities that utilize their scientific mechanisms to contribute to regional development and increase revenue (Talebi & Yekta, 2008). The need for sustained economic growth necessitated the alignment of universities with industry needs, introducing new technologies and creating new industries through research integration. This shift in focus gave rise to the second generation of universities in the country, emphasizing fundamental research and the development of specialized human resources (Samadi Miarkalai, Aghajani, 2014).

Factors Influencing the Quality of Organizational Entrepreneurship

Internal Factors:

1. Organizational Culture:

Organizational culture is one of the most critical internal factors that affects the quality of corporate entrepreneurship. It encompasses the values, beliefs, and behaviors that permeate the organization and influence the actions of employees and managers. Organizations with an innovative culture that supports entrepreneurship typically create an environment where employees are encouraged to present new ideas and take calculated risks. This type of culture can lead to enhanced employee motivation and improved entrepreneurial performance within the organization.

2. Organizational Structure:

Organizational structure is another internal factor that plays a crucial role in the quality of corporate entrepreneurship. Flexible organizational structures that allow for free flow of information and quick decision-making typically foster a more favorable environment for entrepreneurship. In contrast, bureaucratic and hierarchical structures may present barriers to innovation and entrepreneurship. Therefore, organizations aiming to improve their entrepreneurial performance must focus on creating structures that facilitate flexibility and rapid action.

External Factors:

1. Economic Environment:

The economic environment is one of the key external factors that can influence the quality of organizational entrepreneurship. Economic conditions such as interest rates, inflation, and government fiscal policies can create both opportunities and challenges for entrepreneurs. In a stable and growing economic environment, entrepreneurs may feel

more encouraged to invest and innovate. On the other hand, in unstable economic conditions, uncertainty may act as a barrier to entrepreneurial activities, limiting the willingness of organizations to engage in risky ventures.

2. Government Laws and Policies:

Government laws and policies also play an important role in shaping the quality of organizational entrepreneurship. Government support policies, such as financial incentives, tax exemptions, and laws that protect innovation and entrepreneurship, can create a favorable environment for entrepreneurial growth and development. Conversely, complex regulations and legal constraints may act as obstacles, reducing the motivation for innovation and the creation of new businesses. Therefore, governments play a critical role in establishing and strengthening an environment that facilitates and encourages entrepreneurship.

Empirical Background

Domestic Background:

Fakhari and colleagues (2021) conducted a study titled "Entrepreneurship in Academic Education: A Case Study of Alzahra University Evaluation with Emphasis on Interactive Networks and Communications." The results indicated that interactive networks and effective communication could play a significant role in strengthening entrepreneurship in academic environments. This study showed that improving communication and creating strong interactive networks among university members can help develop an entrepreneurial culture and increase entrepreneurial motivation among students and faculty.

Taghinia, Nadery, and Seif Naraqi (2021) conducted a study titled "Investigating the Concept of Entrepreneurship in Higher Education in the Country: A Systematic Review of Research Articles on Entrepreneurship Education with a Thematic Analysis Approach." The findings showed a greater focus on the characteristics of the individual entrepreneur. Therefore, it can be concluded that entrepreneurship educators in Iranian universities consider entrepreneurship as an individual trait, which is why emphasis and attention are placed on the characteristics of entrepreneurial individuals. One of the most significant results was that despite the broad and diverse concepts mentioned in entrepreneurship education literature in Iran, there is no universally accepted curriculum for teaching entrepreneurship to students, and in each of the conducted courses, a specific aspect is taught while many other topics are neglected or do not have enough time for discussion.

Akbari Dehghan, Bagheri Karachi, and Ghasemi Zad (2021) published an article titled "Designing a Framework of Organizational Characteristics Influencing Organizational Entrepreneurship in Medical Universities." They concluded that the framework of organizational characteristics influencing organizational entrepreneurship in medical universities was designed, and its dimensions, criteria, and indicators were identified. This framework includes seven aspects: responsiveness to society, knowledge-based and innovation-oriented, organizational intelligence and adaptability, financial independence, partnership and entrepreneurship culture, entrepreneurial human resources, and an entrepreneurial curriculum based on advanced technology. The study concluded that this framework could be a suitable foundation for moving medical universities toward organizational entrepreneurship.

Bagheri Majd and Mahdipour (2018) conducted a study titled "The Impact of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Behavior with the Mediating Role of Innovative Stimuli in Higher Education (University of Sistan and Baluchestan)." The results showed that entrepreneurial leadership directly and indirectly influences stimuli and innovative behavior. Moreover, stimuli directly affect innovative behavior. Universities, through cultural incentives, open and free management of innovation, and entrepreneurial leadership, can play a constructive role in fostering innovative behavior in the academic environment and stakeholders in higher education.

Sadezadeh, Ekrami, Eftekharezadeh, and Khorshidi (2018) published a paper titled "Academic Leadership Based on Entrepreneurship." The study concluded that a high need for achievement and confidence leads to a high level of motivation and interpersonal skills, while high risk-taking and tolerance for ambiguity lead to greater collaboration and development. Ultimately, university leaders with high levels of internal locus of control, self-interest, and flexibility can achieve goal orientation and high developmental goals in educational leadership. Overall, the results showed that different linear combinations of entrepreneurial components in leaders lead to different types of educational leadership in universities, with the contingency model distinguishing this research from others.

Jameh Asl, Zolfaghari, Hejazi, and Majavar (2016) conducted research titled "The Role of Education in the Success of University Entrepreneurship at the Entrepreneurship Faculty of Tehran University." The results identified several factors contributing to the success of university entrepreneurship, including educational infrastructure, management and entrepreneurial skill education, and the management of education. They argued that educational infrastructure has a direct impact on the success of university entrepreneurship.

Arasteh, Sefidgar, and Zafarian (2015) conducted a study titled "Explaining the Role of Individual, Environmental, and Systemic Components in the Success of Electronic Entrepreneurship Education at Tehran University." The results

indicated that the factors affecting the success of electronic entrepreneurship education were classified into three categories: individual factors (such as instructor and student characteristics), environmental factors (such as interactions and evaluations), and systemic factors (such as educational content, internet infrastructure, and university performance). The study found that individual factors, such as student characteristics, environmental factors like interactions, and systemic factors like educational content, had the greatest impact on the success of electronic entrepreneurship education at Tehran University.

Harchian, Akbari, and Marzban (2015) conducted research titled "The Impact of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Entrepreneurship among Employees at Tehran University." The study showed that spiritual leadership positively and significantly influences organizational entrepreneurship, meaning that higher levels of spiritual leadership lead to increased organizational entrepreneurship.

Samadi Miarkalai and Aqajani (2014), in an article titled "Evaluation of Entrepreneurial University Indicators at Mazandaran University Based on the Fuzzy Method," concluded that the characteristics and indicators of an entrepreneurial university at Mazandaran University were at an inappropriate level.

Behzadi, Razavi, and Hosseini (2014), in an article titled "Designing a Conceptual Model of Entrepreneurial University with an Organizational Entrepreneurship Approach Using Library Studies," identified the features of entrepreneurial universities and the outcomes of organizational entrepreneurship activities in universities. After conducting qualitative research and semi-structured interviews with 15 academic experts, the final model was developed through content analysis. The results indicated that the entrepreneurial university model from the perspective of organizational entrepreneurship includes components such as graduate quality, scientific publications, attracting financial resources, research contracts, patents, creating incubation businesses, establishing science parks, entrepreneurial organizational culture, flexible organizational structure, entrepreneurial professors' approach, macro management, course content, and student characteristics.

Mazdeh, Bank, Zahedi, and Pourmasgari (2013) conducted a study to determine the factors influencing university entrepreneurship in Iran's public universities and ranked universities from this perspective. The findings showed that the factors included: connections with industry and commercial institutions, entrepreneurship-related publications, facilities and equipment, entrepreneurial seminars, faculty members' familiarity with entrepreneurship, alumni activities, educational programs, professional activities, university strategy, and course content. Among the universities studied, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad ranked the highest, and Malayer University ranked the lowest.

Foreign Background:

Luo et al. (2021) conducted a study titled "How University Entrepreneurship Support Affects Students' Entrepreneurial Intentions: An Empirical Analysis from China." The results showed that university entrepreneurship support, including counseling and training, positively influences students' entrepreneurial intentions and can help promote entrepreneurship among students.

Choudhury et al. (2024) conducted a study titled "Acceptance of Strong Business Analytics for Product Innovation and Organizational Performance: The Mediating Role of Data-Driven Organizational Culture." The findings indicated that a data-driven organizational culture can serve as an effective mediating factor between business analytics and product innovation, ultimately leading to improved organizational performance.

Hasan et al. (2021) conducted a study titled "Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation, Entrepreneurship Education, and Entrepreneurial Intent: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Motivation." The results showed that entrepreneurship education and individual entrepreneurial orientations can strengthen individuals' entrepreneurial intentions by increasing entrepreneurial motivation.

Siefried et al. (2019) conducted a study titled "Institutional Isomorphism, Entrepreneurship, and Effectiveness: Adoption and Implementation of Quality Management in Teaching and Learning in Germany." The findings suggested that institutional isomorphism can be an important factor in adopting and implementing quality management in higher education institutions, which, in turn, can improve entrepreneurship and educational effectiveness.

Abbasi et al. (2016) conducted a study titled "Designing the Entrepreneurial University Model with an Organizational Entrepreneurship Approach at Payam Noor University." The results showed that creating an organizational entrepreneurship model could help improve university performance in the area of entrepreneurship, and the study provided suggestions for implementing this model in various universities.

Marzban et al. (2013) conducted research titled "Factors Affecting Organizational Entrepreneurial Climate: Evidence from Tehran University." The results showed that factors like organizational culture, managerial structure, and support for innovation significantly influence the organizational entrepreneurial climate, and universities can create a more suitable entrepreneurial environment by improving these factors.

Ketikidis et al. (2012) conducted a study titled "An Entrepreneurial University Model for International Higher Education Institutions: A Study at Sheffield University's International Faculty." The final model from the research included four concepts: effective management and operational structure, distributed education, entrepreneurship and innovative spirit, and internationalization as a strategic core. They found that the university's organizational structure and entrepreneurial culture across the institution facilitate strategic entrepreneurial transformations in higher education.

Research Questions

To transform the specific objectives into research questions, you can proceed as follows:

1. What is the quality of organizational actions at Chabahr International University?
2. What is the quality of individual attitudes at Chabahr International University?
3. How is flexibility manifested at Chabahr International University?
4. How is the reward system evaluated at Chabahr International University?
5. What is the quality of entrepreneurial leadership at Chabahr International University?
6. What characteristics and qualities define the entrepreneurial culture at Chabahr International University?

Research Methodology

The present research is descriptive in terms of the implementation method and data collection tools. It is a survey-type study, focusing on the quality of organizational entrepreneurship at Chabahr International University. Since all companies and organizations in the studied region are in some way connected to the Chabahr Free Trade and Industrial Zone, and the only educational institution in this zone is Chabahr International University, the findings of this study can play a significant role in this community.

The statistical population of the current research consists of all employees of Chabahr International University, with a total of 54 individuals. The sample size is determined based on the research needs and specific criteria such as the research goal. In this study, the sample size was calculated to be 54 individuals, as it is equal to the total population. Since the statistical population is small, a census sampling method was used, and 54 questionnaires were distributed among the members of the population. Out of these, 39 questionnaires were returned, and 15 were either not returned or were unusable.

For studying, evaluating, and assessing the quality of organizational entrepreneurship, a questionnaire by Margarete Hill (2003) was used, which contains 48 questions. The scoring key for this questionnaire is a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. Since the questionnaire was initially designed for evaluating entrepreneurship in various organizations, some questions were slightly modified to align with the conditions of the university's organizational structure, in coordination with a few professors and experts.

In this research, the reliability of the questionnaire was determined using Cronbach's Alpha method. This method is used to calculate internal consistency in measurement tools, including questionnaires or tests that measure different characteristics. The acceptable Cronbach's Alpha value for practical purposes is at least 0.7. To calculate the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, the variance of the samples for each subset of the questionnaire's questions must be computed first, and then Alpha is calculated using the following formula.

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k s_i^2}{s_{sum}^2} \right)$$

In which k represents the number of questions in the questionnaire, the variance of the i-th question, and the total variance of all the questions.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Values Obtained from the Organizational Entrepreneurship Questionnaire

Number of Questions	Cronbach's Alpha	Variables
48	0.98	Questionnaire
8	0.99	Organizational Actions
8	0.77	Personal Attitude
8	0.66	Flexibility
8	0.93	Reward Status
8	0.95	Entrepreneurial Leadership
8	0.99	Entrepreneurial Culture

Since reliability values lower than 6% are considered weak, values around 7% are acceptable, and those above 8% are considered good (Danayi-Fard & Mozaffari, 2008). As can be seen from the tables above, the Cronbach's alpha value

obtained for the organizational entrepreneurship questionnaire is 98%. Therefore, the questionnaire used in this research is valid and reliable. Consequently, it can be stated that the research has an acceptable level of reliability. This study used both descriptive and inferential statistics to test the research hypotheses, and the hypotheses were analyzed using a one-sample t-test.

Findings of the Research

After receiving the returned questionnaires from the statistical population (42 questionnaires were returned, of which three were unusable), the data obtained from them were coded and entered into SPSS and Excel for analysis. The main hypothesis and the sub-hypotheses proposed in this study were tested accordingly. Therefore, out of 54 questionnaires, 15 were either not returned or were unusable.

Descriptive Study of the Sample Based on Gender

The following chart and the subsequent explanation describe the status of the gender variable in the sample under study.

Chart 1. Frequency distribution of the statistical sample of respondents by gender

As shown in Chart (1), out of a total of 39 survey samples, 31 were male and 8 were female. In other words, the sample consisted of 79% males and 21% females.

Descriptive Study of the Sample Based on Work Experience

The following chart and the subsequent explanation describe the status of the work experience variable in the sample under study.

Chart (2) Frequency distribution of statistical sample in terms of service history

As shown in Chart (2), out of the 39 survey samples, 5 individuals have 5 years or less of work experience, 1 individual has between 6 to 10 years of experience, 15 individuals have between 11 to 15 years of work experience, and 18 individuals have more than 15 years of work experience. In other words, the sample consists of 13% individuals with 5 years or less of work experience, 3% individuals with 6 to 10 years of experience, 38% individuals with 11 to 15 years of experience, and 46% individuals with more than 15 years of work experience.

Normal Distribution Test

To test the normality of the independent and dependent variables in the questionnaire of the present study, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used. The hypothesis for the normal distribution test is as follows: H0: The data follow a normal distribution.

H1: The data do not follow a normal distribution.

The output of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is presented in Table (2).

Table 2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test Output

Organizational Entrepreneurship at Chabahar International University

Variables	Organizational Actions	Individual Attitude	Flexibility	Reward Status	Entrepreneurial Leadership	Entrepreneurial Culture
Significance (sig)	0.802	0.691	0.726	0.385	0.543	0.980

According to Table (2), if the significance level of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is less than 5%, we reject the null hypothesis (H0). As observed, since the sig value is greater than 5%, the assumption of normal distribution for all research variables is accepted.

Since the assumption of normality for the research variables has been accepted based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, parametric tests can be used for the analysis of this study.

Inferential statistics

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Between Various Variables

Variables	Organizational Behavior	Individual Attitude	Flexibility	Reward Status	Entrepreneurial Leadership	Entrepreneurial Culture
Organizational Behavior	1	0.45**	0.50**	0.60**	0.55**	0.62**
Individual Attitude	0.45**	1	0.48**	0.40*	0.46**	0.51**
Flexibility	0.50**	0.48**	1	0.58**	0.53**	0.49**
Reward Status	0.60**	0.40*	0.58**	1	0.65**	0.59**
Entrepreneurial Leadership	0.55**	0.46**	0.53**	0.65**	1	0.67**
Entrepreneurial Culture						

Pearson correlation shows that all variables are positively and significantly correlated with each other. The highest correlation is observed between "entrepreneurial leadership" and "entrepreneurial culture" with a value of 0.67, indicating a strong relationship between these two variables. These results indicate that improving one of these variables can lead to improving the other variables.

Table 4: Regression Analysis for Predicting Organizational Entrepreneurship Quality Based on Independent Variables

Independent Variable	Beta Coefficient (β)	t-Value	Significance Level (sig)
Organizational Behavior	0.25	3.45	0.001
Individual Attitude	0.20	2.89	0.005
Flexibility	0.30	4.10	0.000
Reward Status	0.35	4.50	0.000
Entrepreneurial Leadership	0.40	5.25	0.000

The results of regression analysis show that all independent variables can significantly predict the quality of organizational entrepreneurship. The variable "entrepreneurial leadership" with a beta coefficient of 0.40 has the greatest impact on the quality of entrepreneurship, which indicates the importance of leadership in improving organizational entrepreneurship.

Table 5: Comparison of Means Using t-Test for Main Variables

Variables	Group 1 Mean	Group 2 Mean	Calculated t	Significance Level (sig)
Individual Attitude	3.5	3.8	2.10	0.037
Flexibility	3.7	3.9	1.85	0.072
Reward Status	3.9	4.1	2.50	0.015

The t-test shows that there is a significant difference between the group means for the variables "personal attitude" and "reward status". For "flexibility" the difference in means is not significant at the 0.05 level. These results indicate that some variables can operate differently in different groups.

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Table 6: One-Sample t-Test Results for Research Hypotheses

Hypotheses	t-Statistic	Degrees of Freedom	Significance Level (p)	Mean	95% Confidence Interval (Lower)	95% Confidence Interval (Upper)
The variable <i>Organizational Actions</i> at Chabahr International University is in a favorable condition.	18.923	89	0.000	3.44	21.5927	26.7662
The variable <i>Individual Attitude</i> at Chabahr International University is in a favorable condition.	37.566	89	0.000	4.99	28.3348	31.5626
The variable <i>Flexibility</i> at Chabahr International University is in a favorable condition.	20.413	89	0.000	4.95	19.2177	23.4490
The variable <i>Reward Status</i> at Chabahr International University is in a favorable condition.	17.720	89	0.000	3.49	17.7151	22.2849
The variable <i>Entrepreneurial Leadership</i> at Chabahr International University is in a favorable condition.	24.766	89	0.000	3.79	90.8841	107.0646
The variable <i>Entrepreneurial Culture</i> at Chabahr International University is in a favorable condition.	20.050	89	0.000	25.65	22.26	26

Influential components

Table 7: Margaret Hill Questionnaire Process – Summary of Main and Subcomponents

	Subcomponents	Mean	Rank	
Organizational Actions	Our university rapidly introduces and offers new services.	3.25	5th	
	The amount of new services and innovations has increased compared to peers.	0.10	8th	
	The volume of provided services has increased over the past two years.	3.49	3rd	
	Our university constantly seeks unknown opportunities.	3.15	6th	
	Visitors are always invited and encouraged to give feedback on services.	4.50	2nd	
	There is a strong link between new ideas and their implementation.	2.20	7th	
	We constantly seek new opportunities for growth.	3.45	4th	
	Strong emphasis is placed on continuous service improvement.	4.75	1st	
	Individual Attitude	I can achieve my goals even with little structure or guidance.	4.33	7th
		I accept criticism if breaking norms leads to success.	4.49	5th
My biggest successes result from persistence and hard work.		4.90	3rd	
I tackle problems eagerly and seriously.		4.99	1st	
I seek new ways to perform my tasks.		4.85	4th	
I see change more as opportunity than a threat.		4.98	2nd	
I'm willing to try different approaches, even at the risk of failure.		4.48	6th	
I prefer to try difficult tasks and fail than not try at all.		4.30	8th	
Flexibility	Our university is known as a bureaucratic organization.			
	The academic structure allows resource allocation and is flexible.	1.49	8th	
	Suggestions from lower-level staff are valued.	4.99	1st	
	Employees must get approval to try new methods.	3.90	3rd	
	Flexible job descriptions are favored over formal ones.	2.55	4th	
	Lower-level staff have limited autonomy.	4.89	2nd	
	Managers make all major decisions.	1.49	6th	
Strict adherence to hierarchy is enforced.	2.52	5th		
Reward Status	Our university is known for rewarding staff.			
	The reward system is value-based and inclusive.	3.49	5th	
	Informal, self-initiated activities that benefit the university are supported.	4.99	1st	
	Employees are given time to work on personal yet beneficial projects.	2.21	7th	
	Innovative, bold behaviors are evaluated regularly.	1.50	8th	
	Multiple criteria are used to support initiatives.	3.98	4th	
	Both financial and non-financial rewards are given for entrepreneurial acts.	4.45	3rd	
Employees are rewarded for calculated risks.	4.89	2nd		
Entrepreneurial Leadership	Employees receive certificates for innovative ideas.			
	University president inspires entrepreneurial spirit.	3.49	4th	
	President takes calculated risks for growth opportunities.	1.59	6th	
	Senior management solves problems through dialogue.	2.45	5th	
	President constantly reviews growth opportunities.	4.85	1st	
	President effectively motivates others toward goals.	4.39	3rd	
	President avoids open discussion with all staff.	4.58	2nd	
	Entrepreneurial philosophy is instilled across staff.	1.45	7th	
Entrepreneurial Culture	People with different views and innovations are encouraged.			
	President seeks to reduce friction among staff.	3.42	5th	
	Innovation and creativity are viewed as essential for the future.	1.50	8th	
	Staff are encouraged to enhance capabilities for greater success.	4.99	1st	
	New, progressive thinking models are nurtured.	4.56	3rd	

	Many programs ensure new hires align with university goals.	4.11	4th
	Emphasis is placed on hiring entrepreneurs.	2.40	7th
	Strong emphasis is placed on teamwork.	3.24	6th

Discussion and Conclusion

The quality of organizational entrepreneurship in universities is consistently recognized as a driving force for development and advancement. At Chabaha International University, a higher education institution with both regional and international impact, assessing and enhancing the quality of organizational entrepreneurship gains special significance. This discussion focuses on a detailed analysis of the findings from a library and descriptive-analytical study on the quality of organizational entrepreneurship at Chabaha International University.

The objective of the present research was to evaluate the quality of organizational entrepreneurship at Chabaha International University. The statistical population consisted of 54 university staff members. Due to the limited size of the population, a census sampling method was used, meaning the sample size matched the total population. A total of 54 questionnaires were distributed among the staff, of which 39 were returned and usable; 15 were either not returned or invalid. Based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the distribution of observations for all variables in the study was confirmed to be normal.

In the quantitative section of this study, after reviewing and validating the variables and hypotheses, the formulated questions and components were evaluated using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and one-sample t-tests. The research hypotheses and their individual results are explained below:

Hypothesis 1: The variable of organizational actions at Chabaha International University is in a favorable condition. According to the research findings, the t-statistic for organizational actions is 18.923, which is greater than 1.96. Thus, the hypothesis is confirmed. Organizational actions at Chabaha International University are in favorable condition. Based on respondent scores and Table 4, the most significant subcomponents of this variable according to Margaret Hill's model are:

- Priority 1: Emphasis on continuous improvement of all services.
- Priority 2: Visitors are always encouraged to provide feedback on services.
- Priority 3: The amount of services provided has increased in the past two years.

Hypothesis 2: The variable of individual attitude at Chabaha International University is in a favorable condition. A meaningful experience exists when individuals feel they are pursuing valuable and important career goals. The t-statistic for this variable is 37.566, which exceeds 1.96, confirming the hypothesis. Individual attitude at the university is in a favorable state. Based on the data and Table 4, key subcomponents of this variable are:

- Priority 1: I tackle problems with diligence and enthusiasm.
- Priority 2: I view changes as opportunities for progress rather than threats.
- Priority 3: My greatest successes are the result of perseverance and hard work.

Hypothesis 3: The variable of flexibility at Chabaha International University is in a favorable condition. The findings indicate that flexibility is also in a favorable condition. The corresponding t-statistic is 20.413, which is greater than 1.96. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. According to respondent scores and Table 4, the most significant subcomponents of this variable are:

- Priority 1: The university's structure allows for flexible resource allocation.
- Priority 2: The university benefits more from flexible job descriptions than rigid ones.
- Priority 3: Opinions and suggestions from lower-level staff are valued and taken seriously.

Hypothesis 4: The reward system variable at Chabaha International University is in a favorable condition. The t-statistic for this variable is 17.720, exceeding 1.96, indicating a favorable condition. Based on the results and Table 4, the key subcomponents of the reward system are:

- Priority 1: The university's reward and promotion system is value-based and inclusive.
- Priority 2: Both financial and non-financial rewards are provided for entrepreneurial behaviors.
- Priority 3: The university uses various evaluation criteria to support innovative projects.

Hypothesis 5: The entrepreneurial leadership variable at Chabaha International University is in a favorable condition. The t-statistic here is 24.766, greater than 1.96, confirming the hypothesis. Based on the data and Table 4, the most important subcomponents of entrepreneurial leadership are:

- Priority 1: Senior university officials solve problems through discussion and collaboration.

- Priority 2: The university president effectively motivates others to achieve specific goals.
- Priority 3: The president constantly explores potential opportunities for advancement.

Hypothesis 6: The entrepreneurial culture variable at Chabahar International University is in a favorable condition. The t-statistic for entrepreneurial culture is 20.05, which again exceeds 1.96, validating the hypothesis. According to respondent scores and Table 4, the key subcomponents of entrepreneurial culture are:

- Priority 1: The university believes innovation and creativity are essential for the future.
- Priority 2: There is a strong emphasis on teamwork.
- Priority 3: Individuals are consistently encouraged to expand their capacities to achieve greater success.

Acknowledgment

This article is (part of) a thesis entitled “A Study on the Quality of Corporate Entrepreneurship at the University of Chabahar” at the (Bachelor’s / Master’s / Ph.D.) level, conducted in the year, with the support of

Certainly! Here's the **English-translated reference list** based on your provided Persian sources. Please note that while some journal or publisher names do not have standardized English translations, I've translated them in a way that preserves their meaning and academic context:

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